

BUILDING CONSTRUCTION CONSIDERATIONS METHODS FOR PASSIVE SOLAR BUILDINGS IN CYPRUS

Petros A. Lapithis

University of Nicosia, Department of Architecture P.O.Box 25353, Lefkosia, 1309, Cyprus

Abstract – This paper describes the various paper sizes and formatting requirements of paper submitted

1. INTRODUCTION

Solar architecture, indeed any architecture, cannot persist without being as site-specific as possible. Climate is one of the ultimate site-specification criteria.

Cyprus's climate is within the temperate Mediterranean zone. Its average hottest peak reaches 41°C in the summer and drops to an approximate of 5°C in the winter. Relative humidity ranges from 40-60%, and a large daily temperature range is noted with up to 18°C difference between day and night. Thus Cyprus's climate calls for the need of cooling in the summer and heating in the winter.

2. POLYSTYRENE AS THERMAL INSULATION

Research on extruded and expanded polystyrene for the application on the exterior surfaces of the building has been done by the author. From the research, it was concluded that expanded polystyrene is more cost effective and cheaper than extruded polystyrene. Also it is manufactured in Cyprus while extruded has to be imported. Since one of the goals is to use materials that are derived from the local market, it is one more reason to use expanded polystyrene.

A comparison of different densities of expanded and extruded polystyrene was performed. The U-values of the polystyrene were compared with the thickness and costs on the different structures of the building: (see Figure 7.25, showing the applications on the walls, columns, beams and overhangs)

- Brick wall
- Roof
- Overhangs (on exterior floors)
- Columns and beams

For expanded polystyrene from the Cypriot manufacturing industry Leopol:

1. Density (ρ) of 15 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,036
2. Density (ρ) of 20 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,035
3. Density (ρ) of 25 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,034
4. Density (ρ) of 30 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,033
5. Density (ρ) of 40 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,033

For extruded polystyrene from the Manufacturer Fibran two types are used:

1. Polystyrene used for walls of density (ρ) of 28-30 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,025
2. Polystyrene used for concrete of density (ρ) of 28 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,029

With respect to the type of polystyrene used, the following considerations were evaluated: based on the comparative research of the required structural thickness, against the unit price for several different polystyrene densities, it was determined that in order to meet the required proposed Cyprus Standards, polystyrene of weight 25kg/m³ is to be used. Figure 1 shows the U-values and prices of the Extruded (Polystyrene used for concrete of density (ρ) of 28 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,029) and Expanded (Density (ρ) of 25 kg/m³ and thermal coefficient (λ) of 0,034) polystyrene.

Figure 7.25 Expanded (Leopol) versus Extruded (Fibran) polystyrene

3. MASS APPLICATIONS

The aspects relating to mass are of particular significance for Cyprus due to the large diurnal fluctuations (15 to 25 °C), and the potential possessed by mass for large solar contribution in winter and cooling in summerⁱ. This implies that heat admitted during the day in winter could be stored for use during the evening hours and in the summer could be decapitated in the cool night. Additionⁱⁱ of internal mass incurs energy conservation. On the contrary addition of external mass leads to higher energy consumption. Whereas masonry provides good heat storage medium within a space, it readily passes this heat to the outside when added on exterior walls. Another possible reason could be the quantity of the mass. It appears that the extent of mass increase seems to be critical concerning its effect on the energy loading. Extensive increase of internal mass could act adversely in as far as time needed to cool it in the summer nights or indeed heat it in the winter.

The purpose of internal thermal storage, whether provided by masonry, PCM, water, or the use of smaller windows on the south is to take advantage of “free mass” without danger of overheating, is comfort and energy savings. Thermal mass use can ‘temper’ increased solar gain. Adding thermal capacity reduces temperature swings if the mass is well distributed in the direct gain space.

Placement of thick carpet over heat storage floors and hanging too many plants in sunspace windows are other examples. There is a limit to the positive effect interior mass can have on comfort if it is shielded from effective solar heat absorption. Occupants of passive buildings must be well informed of the necessity for exposure of thermal storage components to direct

sunlight, or to secondary gains via reflection and convection. There have been examples of follow-up owners covering over heat storage walls with insulation and wallboard to “hide” block or brick exposed on the interior, thereby eliminating its storage function. One way to prevent this kind of intervention is to provide a storage mass that is aesthetically acceptable. Also, an operator’s manual for the building explaining the functions and requirements for the mass to work well can be helpful.

Construction of passive solar heat storage ranges from the very simple to the complicated. The simplest heat storage approach is to construct the building of massive structural materials insulated on the exterior to couple the mass to the indoor space. Multiple functions of the components can increase cost effectiveness.

4. EXPERIMENTAL SOLAR HOUSE

The thermal performance of the experimental solar house before the construction phase is analyzed with the purpose of evaluating the ability of different design techniques to provide indoor thermal comfort. Computer simulation softwareⁱⁱⁱ is used which are able to predict in detail the experimental solar house’s effect on the internal environment.

With regard to the size and spatial layout of the solar house, it was decided early on to investigate the present situation in Cyprus in order to find ways of improving the thermal performance of the new housing currently being constructed. In this research, a detached house was used because this represents the worst arrangement from the point of view of a thermal environment.

Thermal mass may not be restricted in the exterior walls. Exterior walls may be insulated and lightweight and interior separating walls can be made with blocks or with concrete, which has a high thermal effusivity. The thermal mass can be located on the floor or on the roof. A thickness of 10cm of a massive material (concrete or brick) is quite suitable for providing coolness for the span of one day or for storing passive heat during a winter day. However, it must be kept in mind that what is important, if the house is indeed well insulated, is the quantity of wall that is in contact with air, rather than the actual thickness of the wall.^{iv}

Another consideration, apart from the U-values, is the skill capacity of the local workmen. The building technique must be easily comprehensible and executable, otherwise care must be taken to find extraordinary workmen.

Planning the Experimental Solar House

It was decided from the early stages of the design, that the house will have an area of close to 200-250m² so as

to approximate the average size of a contemporary house in Cyprus. The final area of the house is 223m². The construction costs should not exceed £80,000, taken into account that this is the construction cost of a typical house^v. Similarly, the house shall have all the most common components of a two level Cypriot house^{vi}.

At the initial stages of the experimental solar house, several passive solar systems were considered. The systems finally chosen were the ones most appropriate for the overheating and under heating periods of the location (See chapter 5).

The construction was decided to be a concrete frame and floors and roof (constructed as the typical Cypriot contemporary home – see chapter 6), 250mm brick work + 70mm expanded polystyrene and plaster on the interior and exterior of the walls. 70mm expanded polystyrene was used to cover the whole building, including walls concrete beams and columns. In this way thermal bridges are excluded.

The roof is constructed by concrete and the beams of the house are reversed so that they will not affect the interior of the design of the top floor. Wood beams and metallic sheets are covering the 600mm reversed beam construction, which shows on the roof. In this way an extra 600mm air cavity is being formed assuring a better insulation. Then on top is covered by the 100mm expanded polystyrene and concrete was used for forming the water canals of the roof.

Typical concrete foundations are used for the anti earthquake calculations (required by the Cyprus governmental laws).

The design demonstrates that with an understanding of the principles of environmental physics, appropriate use of available technology and judicious use of materials and resources, it is possible to achieve comfortable living conditions and low energy use.

Winter indoor temperatures have also been successful. Enough solar heat storage was collected and stored during daytime and released with the appropriate rate in order to maintain pleasant nightly temperature. The fireplace was used to top up the heat on occasions when winter evening temperatures dropped below the norms. In the winter of 2000 these were only 8 times the fireplace was needed and the winter of 2001 these were 10 times. The fireplace was lit on average three to four hours per night and the warmth was retained until well into the next morning.

Figure 7.2 summer design considerations (north-south section through the staircase)

Figure 7.3 winter design considerations (north-south section through the staircase)

Wall construction consideration methods

In the construction of the experimental solar house 13 methods of wall construction were taken under consideration. Upon further examination of all viable options for an efficient passive wall, the following solutions for a masonry-insulated wall were considered (see Table 7.1, 7.2 and 7.3)

For plastering the external wall where polystyrene is placed a special plastering is being used. This is called Adesilex FIS 13 specially used for insulation panels. The reason for this is that typical plastering used on brickwork (mixture of water, cement and sand) will form cracks when placed on polystyrene.

Tables 1,2 & 3 Wall construction consideration methods

<p>1. 100x100x300 brick, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 1.66 W/m²K</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x200x300mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>2. 100x100x300 brick and 70mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and Adesilex FIS 13 on the exterior sides. The plastering on the exterior will be layered on a fibreglass mesh. U-value 0.36 W/m²K</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x200x300mm plaster 10mm expanded polystyrene 70mm Adesilex FIS 5mm</p>
<p>3. 100x200x300 brick, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 1.47 W/m²K</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x200x300mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>4. 100x200x300 brick and 70mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and Adesilex FIS 13 on the exterior sides. The plastering on the exterior will be layered on a fibreglass mesh. U-value 0.31 W/m²K</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x200x300mm plaster 10mm expanded polystyrene 70mm Adesilex FIS 5mm</p>
<p>5. 100x250x300 brick, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 1.37 W/m²K</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x250x300mm plaster 15mm</p>

<p>10. 250mm concrete wall and 70mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and Adesilex FIS 13 on the exterior sides. The plastering on the exterior will be layered on a fibreglass mesh. U-value 0.4 W/m²K</p>	<p>plaster 15mm concrete 250mm expanded polystyrene 70mm Adesilex FIS 5mm</p>
<p>11. 62.5x25x20 Ytong blocks with two layers of special plaster on the inside wall and on the outside with a total price of 37.00 Cyprus pounds per square meter. U-value 0.29 W/m²K.</p>	<p>special plaster 10mm Ytong blocks 62.5x25x200mm special plaster 10mm</p>
<p>12. 500mm adobe wall, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. The plastering on the exterior will be layered on a fibreglass mesh. U-value 1.45 W/m²K</p>	<p>plaster 15mm Adobe 500mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>13. Isorast, which is a lego type block made of polystyrene the cavities are then filled with concrete. 250mm cavity polystyrene wall. 30mm expanded polystyrene on both sides and 190mm of concrete in between the walls, with Adesilex FIS 13 on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 0.46 W/m²K</p>	<p>Adesilex FIS 5mm expanded polystyrene 30mm concrete 190mm expanded polystyrene 30mm Adesilex FIS 5mm</p>

<p>6. 100x250x300 brick and 70mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and Adesilex FIS 13 on the exterior sides. The plastering on the exterior will be layered on a fibreglass mesh. U-value 0.296 W/m²K</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x250x300mm plaster 10mm expanded polystyrene 70mm Adesilex FIS 5mm</p>
<p>7. 250mm cavity brick wall. 100x100x300 brick on both sides and 50mm of air gap in between the walls, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 0.9 W/m²K</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x100x300mm air gap 50mm brick 100x100x300mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>8. 250mm cavity brick wall. 100x100x300 brick on both sides and 50mm of expanded polystyrene in between the walls, with three layers of plaster on the interior and Adesilex FIS 13 on the exterior sides. U-value 0.314 W/m²K</p>	<p>plaster 15mm brick 100x100x300mm expanded polystyrene 50mm brick 100x100x300mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>9. 250mm concrete wall, with three layers of plaster on both the interior and the exterior sides. U-value 3.22 W/m²K</p>	<p>plaster 15mm concrete 250mm plaster 15mm</p>

Adesilex FIS 13 is used for Bonding and exterior finishing of expanded polystyrene or expanded polyurethane, rock wool, cork, etc insulation panels for walls and ceilings directly onto plaster, concrete and cement block. Adesilex FIS 13 is a whitish paste with a synthetic resin base in water dispersion, selected aggregates, and special additives. When mixed with cement, it forms a highly adhesive, highly thixotropic, easily workable mortar that can be applied vertically without sagging and with no slippage even when used for large-size insulating panels. Portland 325 cement is added in proportion of 1 to 1 by weight. An even first layer of the Adesilex FIS 13 mix thick enough to incorporate fibreglass mesh reinforcement (approx. 1-2 mm) is spread. The alkali-resistant fibreglass mesh must be pressed firmly into the fresh layer of the mix with a smooth trowel and must bridge the joints by at least 3-4 cm. After the first layer is dry, a second layer is applied until the mesh is completely covered and the surface is ready to receive its final covering.

For a passive building the walls need thermal mass in order to retain heat. With that in mind, type 11 and 13 listed above are immediately rejected in the case of the solar house. Types 11 and 13 can be used for passive buildings as long as the walls will not be used as thermal mass.

Since the U-value of the wall is an important factor, types 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9 are rejected since they have an unacceptable U-value.

Type 10 and 12 have an acceptable U-value, but the high manufacturing cost does not make them cost efficient.

The types 2, 4, 6, 7 and 8 are viable options. Type 6, 7 and 8 seems to be the best of at of the 25cm thickness of the concrete frame of the building (beams and columns). A better architectural design is achieved by avoiding the 5cm gap between the external walls and the columns and beams.

With these comparisons in mind, the chosen type of wall construction for the Experimental Solar House is type 6, since it effectively insulates the whole structure and avoids thermal bridges where the columns and beams occur.

Roof construction consideration methods

In the construction of the experimental solar house two methods of roof construction were taken under consideration. Upon further examination of all viable options for an efficient passive roof, the following solutions were considered (see Table 7.4).

Table 7.4 Roof construction consideration methods

<p>1. 150mm concrete, 3mm water insulation and 100mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and 50mm on the exterior. U-value - 0.29 W/m²K.</p>	<p>possible final layer water barrier 3mm plaster 50mm exp. pol. 100mm vapour barrier concrete 150mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>2. 150mm concrete, 3mm water insulation, with three layers of plaster on the interior and 50mm concrete on the exterior sides. U-value 3.03 W/m²K. (Figure 8.16)</p>	<p>water barrier 3mm plaster 50mm concrete 150mm plaster 15mm</p>
<p>3. 150mm concrete, 600mm air gap, 3mm water insulation and 100mm of expanded polystyrene on the exterior, with three layers of plaster on the interior and 50mm on the exterior. U-value - 0.28 W/m²K. (Figure 8.15)</p>	<p>possible final layer water barrier 3mm plaster 50mm expanded polystyrene 100mm metal sheet W-shaped 50mm wooden beams 100*100mm air gap 600mm concrete 150mm plaster 15mm</p>

For a passive building the structure need thermal mass in order to retain heat. With that in mind all three roof types are a viable option. Type 1 and 3 are the best. A better interior architectural design is achieved by using type 3, because of the reverse beam structure of the roof. Also a better insulation is achieved while avoiding the 5cm gap between the external walls and the columns and beams. The Experimental Solar House uses type 3.

Monitoring the Experimental Solar House

Hourly temperature and relative humidity readings were taken all year round. The temperature range acceptable for comfort is from 19°C to 29°C for Cyprus^{vii}.

The house was first inhabited in May 2000. The daytime external temperature reached approximately 28°C and the nighttime temperature was 14°C. The indoor temperature, however, remained steady at around 22°C.

Overall, the 24hour indoor measurements indicate a variation of 0-2°C- temperature swing. Taking into account that the external temperature swing is 10-15°C, this shows that a constant temperature is preserved throughout the day. Depending from the external temperatures the internal temperatures range from 19°C to 29°C.

The only energy used in the Experimental Solar House is electricity, potable water and wood for auxiliary heating. the house rewarded the inhabitants with a low winter and summer utility bill, considering that no air conditioning system is required. There is an energy saving of 85% comparing the contemporary house with the solar house.

Lessons learned

1. It is necessary to consider the total energy use, and not focus on space and/or water heating alone. It is, for example, important to consider both heating and cooling, as focusing on one season could only lead to problems during the other season. In addition, reducing cooling loads was often a greater challenge than reducing heating loads.
2. It is necessary to consider the building as a system, where the different technologies used are integral parts of the whole. The order in which the technologies are introduced into the design appears to be quite important. Generally, energy-conservation technologies are considered first, passive solar second, and active solar third, in most cases all of these technologies are used, often in a combination of systems.

3. Energy conservation, using high levels of insulation and super-windows, should be the first option considered. High levels of insulation are beneficial in the climatic conditions of Cyprus, as well as in countries where cooling is a major issue.
4. Passive solar gains can offer a major contribution to space heating in the climatic conditions of Cyprus and do not lead to overheating if proper solar protection is used. Passive solar cooling also proved to work. In both the heating and the cooling situations it was necessary to include thermal mass in the direct gain passive solar designs, as is extended the usability of the systems by increasing the time constant and slowing down heat build-up in the summer.
5. Designing new, innovative building concepts requires a multi-disciplinary design team. The extensive uses of solar technologies, which are often integral parts of the design, make the design process different from traditional methods. It requires the energy aspects to be considered from the early design stage, and also requires the architects, engineers and the clients' collaboration from the beginning.
6. Training of constructors and on-site supervision is particularly important in low-energy buildings. In very low-energy buildings, the energy consumption is strongly influenced by construction practices and by user behaviour than in conventional buildings. For instance, air tightness and the avoidance of thermal bridges is much more important in a well-insulated building than in a traditional building.

5. CONCLUSION

What one can conclude from the passive solar design discussed in this research is that, for the climate of Cyprus or any given climate, there are a number of choices of solar techniques from which to select, each with advantages and disadvantages that must be weighed in terms of the local climate, construction practice and competing fuel costs.

Taking into account the advantages and disadvantages of the passive solar system it is concluded that the best systems which can be used for the Experimental Solar House are the following:

- Direct Gain
- Thermal Insulation
- Thermal Storage (Interior Mass)
The simplest heat storage approach is to construct the building of massive structural materials insulated on the

exterior, to couple the mass of the indoor space

- Glazing
Types to be used: Low emmissivity glazing, argon-filled, double-glazed, special glass panes
Vertical Glazing Surfaces would intercept almost as much radiation during heating season as optimally sloped surfaces. Shading can be easily controlled for the non-heating season.
- Solar Control
By use of: orientation, shading devices.
- Natural Ventilation
By use of: cross ventilation, stack effect, night ventilation and ceiling fans

However, preliminary recommendations regarding the above-mentioned passive solar means may not be adequate to state that a particular building will not be overheated in the summer or underheated in winter. A proper assessment regarding such decisions cannot be made without calculations that involve a suitable prediction method of indoor air temperatures and numerical external and internal design data.

Most building in Cyprus are constructed with little or no insulation, thus causing a high percentage of summer and winter discomfort. The Experimental Solar House is designed in accordance to comfort zone calculations so as to ensure the maximum comfort of its occupants. The wall and roof construction plays a significant role in the insulation of the house.

Vertical and horizontal louvers, although considered, were decided upon not being 100% suitable, due to the high construction cost and permanent view obstruction of the east and west façade of the house. The second floor bedroom windows on the southeast and south walls were recessed so as to prevent summer sun from entering, but allowing winter warmth to enter. They are used as permanent shading devices. Roof fans are used to assure no overheating would occur in the extreme overheated periods.

Thus the construction of the solar house has a purpose that is multifaceted. It is an environmental success as well as an architectural one. The house itself is able to provide excellent indoor air quality and natural lighting.

When a Cypriot contemporary house was compared to a traditional house, the energy performance of the original insulated traditional house is superior to the contemporary house, with no energy-efficient considerations. Therefore, since the Experimental Solar House was designed and constructed using researched material of traditional houses, once compared with a

contemporary house the results were easy to assume. The Experimental Solar House proved to be far superior in its energy-saving performance.

ⁱ Sergides, D. “*Zero Energy for The Cyprus House*”, The Architectural Association, 1991

ⁱⁱ Sergides, D. “*Zero Energy for The Cyprus House*”, The Architectural Association, 1991

ⁱⁱⁱ Lapithis, P, *Solar Architecture in Cyprus*, PhD theses, University of Wales, UK, 2002

^{iv} Dr Flourenzou Flourenzos, Energy Engineering, Laboratoire d’Energie Solaire et de Physique du Batiment, Lozahn, Switzerland.

^v Stavrou, N. “*Energy Conservation in new residential buildings in Cyprus-Cost comparative study*”, School of the Built Environment, University of Glamorgan, Cardiff, Wales, May 1998

^{vi} Lapithis, P, *Solar Architecture in Cyprus*, PhD theses, University of Wales, UK, 2002

^{vii} Lapithis, P, *Solar Architecture in Cyprus*, PhD theses, University of Wales, UK, 2002